

EFFECT OF TUGLISID ON MORPHOLOGIC AND MORPHOMETRIC FEATURES OF RABBIT LIVER

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Abstract. *Sequential studies in experimental and intact rabbits have shown that in intact rabbits migration of the granular component of the nucleus core occurs even under physiologic conditions, and migration of the nucleus core GC was observed to a greater extent when Tuglisid was administered for hepatoprotection.*

Keywords: *liver, hepatocyte, nucleus, granular component, rabbit.*

Relevance: In the 60s of the last century, it was described in oocytes of lower animals (Raikova, 1968, Raven, 1962, Davidson, 1972, Miller, 1966, Tabler, 1975). At the same time, it has been found that before exit, the GCN increases in volume many times, i.e. its amplification occurs (Krshi, 1972). This process is associated with the need for a huge amount of protein for the full development of the embryo (Kessel, 1969, Scharer, Wuizelman, 1969). In this connection, it was initially assumed that it was characteristic only of oocytes, i.e. germ cells with a haploid set of chromosomes. Subsequent studies showed that it can also occur in somatic cells of lower vertebrates, especially secreted gland-forming cells (Shubnikova, Kirpichnikova, and Levinson, 1962). In the work of E.A. Shubnikova, (1966) it is assumed that the nucleus of a hepatic cell (river crayfish hepatopancreas) participates in secretion production by reducing nuclear structural (Feulgen-positive) substances. Similarly, nuclei extrusion occurs in the bissus gland of the mussel, which served as a basis for a schematic presentation of the sequential stages of this process in a textbook on histology (Kirpichnikova and Levinson). However, hepatocytes, unlike germ cells, are diploid, moreover, polyploid cells (Kudryatsev B.N. et al. 1986, Zatsepina O.V., 1992). In this connection, it can be assumed that the increase in the volume of the nucleus is caused not only by the usual synthesis of ribosomal genes (organizers of the nucleus DNA), but also by their multiple amplification, accordingly to the ploidy of cells. When passing through the nuclear membrane, it is evidently enveloped by it, similarly to the way pinocytosis is carried out by the plasmolemma or secretory granules are enclosed in the membranes of the Golgi complex (E.V. Raikova, 1968, Scharer and Wypzelman, 1979). Probably, this is the reason why the vague contours of the GC after exit into the cytoplasm becomes smooth and the shape - strictly globular. The exit of larger fragments of nucleus material, as it is labeled in the literature as “elimination of extrachromosomal material” was also found in oocytes of various insects, crustaceans, fish and amphibians (Har, 1967, Scharer, Wuizmann, 1979). The extrusion of mammalian GCNs, which we have discovered, although by the mechanism of flow is similar to the release of nuclei in lower vertebrates, the significance of this process remains undisclosed.

Objective. To study morphologic and morphometric aspects of the nuclear apparatus of hepatocytes in rabbits in normal and under stimulation.

Materials and methods of research. When performing this work, liver tissue was used. From laboratory animals we used sexually mature rabbits (n=22) of both sexes, weighing 2,5-3,0 kg, 8 of them served as a control, they received reg os - physiological solution, 14 - experimental animals, which during a month were administered intragastrically 10 mg/kg “Tuglisid”. To

conduct scientific experimental research on laboratory animals, permission of the Ethical Committee under the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, minutes of the 8th meeting of December 2, 2021, was obtained. Experimental research was conducted according to ethical standards for humane treatment of experimental animals, in compliance with the criteria of the world community and the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrates used for experimental and other purposes (Strasbourg, 1986).

For histological studies, liver tissue slices were embedded in paraffin wax after fixation in 12% neutral formalin solution and standard treatment. Sections were stained with hematoxylin-eosin for histological studies. Histochemical methods were used to detect DNA and RNA; DNA was detected by Völgen and RNA by Brasher.

The preparations were photographed using a microscope model DN-300m, with a digital photo attachment, connected to a computer. ImageJ-win64 computer programs were used for morphometric study of the data. For this purpose, random fields of view of histological preparations were photographed using a microscope model DN-300m, with a digital photo attachment, connected to a computer. The finished microparameters were viewed with a SARL Zeiss Microcopy GmbH microscope and photographed with an Axio Lab camera A1 (Germany). Morphometric studies were performed according to the method of Avtandilov (2) and processed in Axiovision program (Russia, Far East).

Result: Rabbit liver was examined on the 30th day after administration of Tuglisdid. Light-optically, the liver of rabbits, like many other mammals, is represented by numerous lobules, the boundaries of which are not clearly expressed, and the lobules themselves consist of hepatic plates and sinusoidal capillaries oriented to the central vein. Capillary walls consist of endothelial and stellate cells (Kupffer cells). Hepatocytes are arranged in 2-3 rows and have a polygonal shape. The oxyphilically stained cytoplasm in the center contains one or two nuclei (Figure 1). The area of hepatocytes is $246.6 \pm 03.7 \text{ mkm}^2$ and the area of nucleus is $89.7 \pm 1.1 \text{ mkm}^2$. Uninucleated hepatocytes are more common, and binucleated hepatocytes are less common. Up to 8.0 binucleated hepatocytes can be seen in a single field of view. Hepatocytes with medium-sized nuclei are more common. One or two, rarely 3-4 nuclei are detected in the nucleus. The nuclei are usually small in size, only in some nuclei larger nuclei are detected, and they are located in the center of the karyoplasm (Fig. 1.B).

In some cases, nuclei in the form of a dense tangle are found directly under the nuclear membrane. It is important to note that in these cases, the contours of the nuclei are not clear and merge with the karyoplasm. In Fig. 1.A, two dense bodies located next to the nucleus are clearly visible on the overview image. At high microscope magnifications (for precise clarification we used the maximum magnification of a modern digital microscope, ca. 10 and vol. 100, which is 1000x magnification of the object). In Figure 1.B, the dark calf is outside the nuclear membrane (large and dark), while inside the nucleus a similar formation is small in size, light colored with indistinct contours. The other two corpuscles are outside the nucleus, but have rounded outlines and dense appearance, but differ in volume. As mentioned above, dark corpuscles appear more often on the periphery of the hepatic lobule, which is confirmed by this figure.

The juxtaposition of all these phenomena indicate that they represent migrated GCs. In those cases when the calf is at some distance from the nucleus and acquires clear contours, it is probably due to its envelopment by the karyolemma. In addition, during migration of the calf, its volume slightly increases and the nucleoloplasm becomes luminescent. It should be noted that

migration of HAs from the nucleus to the cytoplasm like mitosis is a very rare phenomenon; nevertheless, HA migration is much more frequent than mitosis when Tuglisid is administered.

Fig. 1. Rabbit liver after administration of Tuglisid. Coloration: Hematoxylin-eosin.
A. Morphologic picture of hepatic laminae, sinusoidal capillaries, and hepatocytes. The nuclei of polygonal hepatocytes contain one or two nuclei. Uv.10x40.
B. Same case. Appearance of a dense rounded cell in the cytoplasm of hepatocyte. Uv ob.10x10 (immersion).

Fig. 2. Rabbit liver during administration of Tuglisid. Hematoxylin-eosin staining.
A. Peripheral zone of the hepatic lobule, two hepatocytes have a release of HAs into the cytoplasm. In the upper part of the figure GCs are small in size, in the lower part are larger and rounded, both have a dense appearance. Eq.10 x 40.
B. Same case, output of three GCs, explanation in the text. Eq. 10x10

This is confirmed by Fig. 2.B, where three nuclei migrate at once, and each of them is at a different stage of moving from the nucleus to cytoplasm. In the upper right part of the figure, the GC is literally at the stage of exit through the nuclear membrane, at least a fragment of the nucleus is projected above the nucleus and has not clear contours. In the lower part of the figure, the nucleus has just separated from the nucleus (the contours are also not clear, but it is outside the nucleus), and in the center of the figure, the nucleus has significantly separated from the nucleus (the contours are smooth and even). It is important to note that migrated HAs appear near the nucleus or at some distance from the nucleus, and sometimes they are freely located in the cytoplasm out of connection with the nucleus.

Fig. 3. Rabbit liver after administration of Tuglisid.

Hematoxylin-eosin staining.

A. Migrated GCN of small size, rounded shape with smooth contours. Eq. 10x10.

B. The released HA in the cytoplasm takes on a rounded shape, less dense consistency, but slightly increased in volume. Eq. 10x10

In any case, after migration of GCs into cytoplasm, there is an increase in their volume with rounding of their contour, which is probably associated with their envelopment by the nuclear envelope. Under the action of Tuglisid, most often one HA migrates from the nucleus, but in rare cases we detected a simultaneous exit of two nuclei from a mononuclear or binuclear hepatocyte (Fig.4.A). When staining liver slices for DNA by Feulgen, we noted that Feulgen-positive substances were not detected in the cytoplasm of the hepatocyte (Fig.4.B). In any case, the secreted nucleus transforms from a small dense cotyledon into a rounded larger body, the significance of which remains unknown. In addition, during migration of GCs, we paid attention to the state of cytoplasm, cell boundaries, and relationships with neighboring cells. Our observations showed that the boundaries did not change significantly, i.e. separation of the cell from neighboring hepatocytes, or separation of the cytoplasm in the form of cytotomy was also not observed. In general, examination of the liver during administration of Tuglisid preparation showed that hepatic laminae are well preserved and hepatocytes have usual structure, the state of sinusoids, portal

tracts, epithelium of bile ducts without significant changes, no phenomena of dystrophy or destruction of parenchymatous elements were observed.

Fig. 4. Rabbit liver after administration of Tuglized.

A. Hematoxylin-eosin staining. Peripheral part of the lobule. In the center of the figure is a binuclear hepatocyte with two isolated HAs, the structure of which differs from that of the nuclei. Eq.10 x10.

B. Same case. Feigen staining of DNA. The nuclear content is stained pink. The release of part of the nuclear material is not visible. Eq. 10x10.

Thus, our studies have shown that the new drug Tuglized does not show side effects on the structural elements of the liver, on the contrary, it improves the state of hepatic cells, specifically affecting the activity of hepatocyte nuclei, stimulates the migration of HA from the nucleus to the cytoplasm. Comparison of the topography of the various nuclei as well as histochemical reactions to RNA (Fig.5A.B) strongly suggested that they are migrating GCs that penetrate through the nuclear envelope, are probably enveloped by it, and in the cytoplasm acquire smooth contours and increase somewhat in volume, but the further fate of these nuclei remains unclear. The data obtained during the introduction of a new domestic drug Tuglized, was subject to verification, for this phenomenon could be specific, i.e. characteristic of rabbits, or indeed could be the result of the action of the new drug. To verify these assumptions, we conducted an additional experimental study in 14 rabbits with an initial weight of 2.5 - 3.0 kg, it was decided to analyze the histological picture of liver cells of normal healthy rabbits. Histological preparations were prepared from the obtained pieces of liver tissue, which were subjected to morphological analysis after staining. The area of hepatocytes is $228.6 \pm 3.7 \text{ mkm}^2$, and the nucleus is equal to $874 \pm 1.3 \text{ mkm}^2$.

Hepatocytes contain from one to 3-4 nuclei. The number of bi-nucleated hepatocytes is $3.6 \pm 0,1$ in one field of view. In rats, the number of nuclei is the same, but one large nucleus is more often found, with clumps of chromatin around it.

Figure 5. Rabbit liver during administration of the drug Tuglisid.

A. Stage of GC penetration through the nuclear envelope. Brasher staining

B. Same case. Phelgen staining, no Phelgen-positive substances in the cytoplasm of hepatocytes. Eq.10 x10 (immersion).

It should be noted that at the beginning, a long search of the entire liver parenchyma did not yield the desired results. However, bearing in mind that hepatocyte nuclei localized near portal tracts migrate most often, we began to analyze these areas thoroughly. As a result, in some areas, dense cells very similar to the migrating nuclei of experimental animals were detected. The portal tract in the liver includes a peripheral portion of the lobule in which a small amount of connective tissue is usually localized along with the hepatic triad. These formations are distinct from each other and are surrounded by a thin network of fibrous connective tissue. From these structures, the hepatic laminae originate, which are composed of hepatocytes. Usually these hepatocytes do not differ from others, their cytoplasm is oxiphilic and their nuclei are sharply basophilic. Among hepatocytes, both uninucleated and binucleated hepatic cells are found. In such periportal areas, small dense corpora are found in the cytoplasm of hepatocytes. The detected corpuscles resemble the migrating HAs of rabbits after administration of Tuglisid, and dense corpuscles were detected in four hepatocytes, although no direct exit from the nucleus was observed among them. Histochemical study of the rabbit liver showed that the nuclei of hepatocytes when stained with pyronin according to Brasher are revealed in the form of rounded bodies of crimson color. When staining for RNA, as usual, hepatocytes contain from one to 3-4 nuclei. A search for migrating nuclei showed that some of them move from the nucleus into the cytoplasm of the hepatocyte (see Fig. 6).

Thus, although specifically escaping HAs from the nucleus through the nuclear envelope into the cytoplasm of hepatocytes were not found among periportal cells, they were detected away from the nucleus, loosely localized in the cytoplasm of hepatocytes. The similarity of these corpuscles to the corpuscles detected in rabbits during administration of Tuglisid indicates that in rabbits in this zone, apparently, there is a cambial zone where, along with mitosis, HAs migrate

from the nucleus to the cytoplasm of the hepatocyte, which can be considered as one of the mechanisms of liver regeneration.

Figure 6. Rabbit liver. Brasher staining. RNA in the hepatocyte nucleus is revealed as rounded crimson-colored cells.

A. Two centrally located hepatocytes have distinct nuclei, one located in the karyoplasm, the other - in tight contact with the nuclear envelope.

B. In the center of the figure several hepatocytes contain a nucleus, each differently localized in the karyoplasm, in one of them swelling of HA from the nucleus into the cytoplasm is noted. Eq. Ob.10 x 10

Conclusion: Sequential studies of experimental and intact rabbits showed that in intact rabbits' migration of the granular component of the nucleus core occurs even under physiologic conditions, and migration of the nucleus core GC was observed to a greater extent when Tuglisid was administered for hepatoprotection. The migrated granular component is located at a distance from the nucleus, swollen, enlarged and rounded. Extrusion of nucleus GCs is 2.3 times higher than in intact animals, which proves that the drug Tuglisid enhances GC migration. Due to the fact that the process is especially intensified during the introduction of the new drug Tuglisid, we can conclude that this phenomenon is probably important in the regenerative processes of the liver and may be, along with mitosis, an indicator of regenerative processes. The migration of the nucleus is of such importance because mitosis leads to an increase in the number of cells, the migration of the HCN probably contributes to increased protein synthesis. Migration of the SCN appears to enhance protein synthesis, a very necessary product for the new formation of intracellular structures, as a consequence of which cell division occurs to restore the lost part or to grow the organism.

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